

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART V. ACTION OF ACID CHLORIDES
ON COPPER DIACETYLACETONE

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The action of carbonyl chloride, oxalyl chloride and malonyl chloride on copper diacetylacetonate results respectively in the formation of diacetylcyclobutane-dione, diacetylcyclopentane-trione and diacetylcyclohexane-trione, which is most stable. Diacetylcyclobutane-dione is very unstable being broken into two molecules of acetyl keten which recombine in a different manner to form dehydracetic acid thereby confirming Feist's formula for the substance.

Deshapande and co-workers have given the structure (I) to diacetylacetonate (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 596; 1935, 12, 466). Copper salt of the triketone on this basis should be represented by (II) and therefore it should be possible to replace the copper by suitable groups by the action of acid chlorides *e.g.*, carbonyl chloride in this manner should give cyclobutane-1:3-dione (III).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

Copper diacetylacetonate and carbonyl chloride react in molecular proportion to give a solid, m.p. 110°. The analysis agrees with the formula (C₈H₈O₄) which is that of the *cyclobutane-dione* (III) and it was thought that the desired substance was obtained but the reactivity of one carbonyl group instead of two or four could not be explained. The melting point suggested that the new compound may be dehydracetic acid C₈H₈O₄ (IV), though the possibility was remote. It is surprising to note that the mixed melting point with an authentic sample of dehydracetic acid gives no depression. A series of the following derivatives from the new compound and (IV) have been found identical: Copper salt, semicarbazone and *para*-nitrophenylhydrazone. This left no doubt as to the identity of the new compound with dehydracetic acid.

It is difficult to realise the formation of dehydracetic acid, unless we assume the instability of *cyclobutane-dione* (III). Then it seems likely that the compound (III) is undoubtedly formed at first which undergoes ring fission due to the instability of the *cyclobutane-dione* ring giving rise to two molecules of acetyl keten which then recombine in a different manner to form one molecule of dehydracetic acid (IV) as shown above (*cf.* Chick and Willmore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 946). This incidental synthesis of dehydracetic acid proves that the structure (IV) assigned to it by Feist is correct and that Collie's structure is unlikely. This has been proved by Rasweiler and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2758) on other grounds also.

It is important to note that the action of nitrophenylhydrazine on dehydracetic acid seems to be somewhat different from that of phenylhydrazine which in molecular proportion gave the pyrazole derivative (V) (Stole, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3026). With nitrophenylhydrazine a simple nitrophenylhydrazone is formed. It is not easy to say which of the three carbonyl groups has yielded to phenylhydrazone formation. But as far as one could go by analogy, the nitrophenylhydrazone has probably the structure (VI).

The action of oxalyl chloride on copper diacetylacetonate gives the expected diacetyl *cyclopentane-trione* (VII). In this reaction much carbon dioxide is evolved showing that the compound (VII) is not the only product of the reaction and must be accompanied by other side products. The diacetyl *cyclopentane-trione* is a solid, m.p. 176°. It gives colouration to ferric chloride and does not form a copper salt. It is rather unstable and when left in contact with water, it hydrolyses to diacetylacetonate and oxalic acid which were isolated and identified. It forms a pentasemicarbazone.

Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 305) has pointed out that the lower cyclic monoketones like *cyclopropanone* are less stable than their corresponding polymethylenes; while the higher cyclic monoketones are more stable than their corresponding polymethylenes. The stability of the compounds (III) and (VII) is in agreement with this view although it is to be noted that the number of the ketonic groups in (III) is two and in (VII) is three

Proper comparison would be afforded between (VII) and diacetyl *cyclohexane-trione* (VIII) which is obtained by the action of malonyl chloride on copper diacetylacetonone.

Diacetyl*cyclohexane-trione* is a pale yellow solid, m.p. 171° and unlike (VII) it is more stable and could be boiled with aqueous alcohol without rupture of the ring. This is the effect of introducing one methylene group in the molecule of (VII). Since diacetyl*cyclohexane-trione* (VIII) is a derivative of *s-cyclohexane-trione* (IX) which is tautomeric to phloroglucinol (X), a resemblance between (VIII) and (X) is expected. This has been realised. Like phloroglucinol it is slightly acidic and gives an intense violet colour to ferric chloride. It dissolves in caustic soda, which with excess of alkali darkens on exposure to air as happens in the case of phloroglucinol and more readily in the case of pyrogallol. Like the latter it reduces alkaline copper sulphate, though somewhat slowly.

Phloroglucinol in a sealed tube with zinc chloride and acetic anhydride at 150° gives the triacetyl derivative (XII) but when refluxed with acetic anhydride gives 1 : 3 : 5-triacetate (XIII). Diacetylphloroglucinol (VIII) when boiled with acetic anhydride gives a compound m.p. 115° of the composition $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$ which is that of the monoacetyl derivative (XI). Theoretically a triacetyl derivative is expected but probably the two acetyl groups in the molecule of (VIII) interfere with the migration of two hydrogen atoms marked with asterisk to form a tri-enolic structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper diacetylacetonone (II) was prepared by adding to a cold alcoholic solution of diacetylacetonone a saturated solution of copper and sodium acetates when the apple green coloured copper diacetylacetonone precipitated as a crystalline solid. It was washed free from copper acetate and dried at 110°, yield almost theoretical.

Action of Carbonyl Chloride on Copper Diacetylacetonone : Formation of Dehydracetic Acid.

—To a suspension of copper salt (16 g.) in dry benzene (70 c.c.) in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a good cork carbonyl chloride in benzene (57 g., 14.4%) was gradually added

in about three quarters of an hour under ice-cooling. The reaction flask was kept in ice-chest for 4 days when the reaction was complete and the benzene layer became dark orange in colour which was filtered and the gummy mass on washing with hot benzene left copper chloride in the funnel. The benzene extract was washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and after removing the excess of benzene the residual liquid crystallised out as yellow needles on cooling in a basin. This was recrystallised from dilute alcohol as beautiful pale yellow needles, m.p. 110°. (Found : C, 58.0; H, 5.5. $C_8H_8O_4$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of dehydracetic acid was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol as colourless shining needles, m.p. 198-99° (decomp.). Bülow and Fisher (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4161) recorded m.p. 197-98°. This was found identical with the semicarbazone prepared from a genuine specimen of dehydracetic acid.

The *nitrophenylhydrazone* (VI) was prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of the substance and a little more than one molecule of *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine for 20 minutes on a water-bath. This was filtered hot and on cooling the nitrophenylhydrazone separated, which was crystallised from acetic acid as short thick brown needles, m.p. 226-27° (decomp.). (Found : C, 55.6; H, 4.8; N, 14.4. $C_{14}H_{13}O_5N_3$ requires C, 55.4; H, 4.3; N, 13.9 per cent).

Action of Oxalyl Chloride on Copper Diacetylacetonone : Formation of Diacetylcyclopentane-trione (VII).—Copper salt (15 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (80 c.c.) in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a calcium chloride tube and oxalyl chloride (9.5 g., 1 mol) was added gradually in an hour under ice-cooling. Slow effervescence could be seen in the flask and a small quantity of gas was being evolved which was identified to be carbon monoxide. The reaction flask as before was left in ice for 4 days and after the reaction was over, the contents were filtered at the pump when a black gritty mass was left on the funnel. This was rubbed with water to remove copper chloride, dried on a porous plate and again washed with benzene to remove the colour when the diacetyl *cyclopentane-trione* was left as a brown solid, yield 8 g. It crystallised from ethyl acetate as short shining star-shaped needles, m.p. 176° (decomp.). (Found : C, 54.6; H, 3.9. $C_8H_8O_3$ requires C, 55.1; H, 4.1 per cent). 0.086 G. of the substance reacted with 4.43 c.c. *N*/10-caustic soda and 4.38 c.c. are required theoretically.

On working up the benzene layer a small quantity of a solid insufficient for further work was obtained which when crystallised from ethyl acetate melted at 170°.

Hydrolysis of Diacetylcyclopentane-trione.—The aqueous washings of the black gritty mass consisting of (VII) contained copper chloride and some of the substance (VII). From this solution a light blue coloured copper salt separated on standing for some time which on decomposing with concentrated hydrochloric acid on warming and ether extraction gave a crystalline acid which was characterised as oxalic acid by its m.p. and reactions.

The remaining aqueous filtrate after removal of copper oxalate above on extraction with hot ethyl acetate gave a sweet smelling liquid which solidified on scratching, m.p. 50°. This was identified as diacetylacetonone by its small, colour reaction to ferric chloride, m.p. and the formation of copper salt by comparison with a genuine sample of diacetylacetonone.

Action of Water on Diacetylcyclopentane-trione.—A little of the pure crystallised substance melting at 176° was dissolved in water and left for some time. The solution was divided in two parts. To one portion on adding copper and sodium acetates and warming a green coloured copper salt was precipitated at once which on decomposition with dilute hydrochloric acid gave diacetylacetone. To the second portion was added copper chloride when a light blue coloured copper salt was formed the quantity increasing on warming, which on decomposition with warm strong hydrochloric acid and ether extraction gave oxalic acid.

The *penta-semicarbazone* of (VII) crystallised from dilute acetic acid as small white needles, m.p. 259° (decomp.). (Found : N, 43.3. $C_{14}H_{13}O_5N_6$ requires N, 43.8 per cent).

Diacetylcyclohexane-trione (VIII).—Copper diacetylacetone (5 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (30 c.c.) in a flask and malonyl chloride (3.5 g.) diluted with an equal volume of dry benzene was gradually added under efficient ice-cooling. The flask was corked and left in ice for a day and after filtering the supernatant red benzene layer, the residual semi-solid mass was stirred with water. The thick dark green coloured liquid which resulted on stirring with water was filtered and allowed to crystallise. After standing for a day the crystalline solid separating was filtered, washed free of copper chloride and dried, yield 1.5 g.

It is a pale yellow solid and could be crystallised from alcohol or glacial acetic acid as star-shaped needles, m.p. 171° . (Found : C, 56.8; H, 4.4. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent.). It is sparingly soluble in benzene or ether, is slightly soluble in water and does not form a semicarbazone like diacetylcyclopentane-trione (VII).

The *acetyl derivative* (XI) was prepared by boiling the compound (VIII) with excess of acetic anhydride and a drop of sulphuric acid and pouring the dark coloured liquid formed in water when a small quantity of gummy mass separated which was filtered and pressed on a porous tile. The filtrate on evaporation gave a solid mixed with gum which was also pressed on the tile. The two products were separately rubbed with petrol ether and on extraction with hot benzene the acetyl derivative separated as a crystalline solid on cooling, m.p. 115° . (Found : C, 57.6; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent.).